

Research-in-Progress Paper

Beyond the niche: Supporting transformative change in Living Labs with a practice-oriented typology and a management tool

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Abstract

Living labs (LLs) are key instruments for fostering local and regional socio-technical transitions, yet research on factors supporting or hindering their success remains fragmented. This study develops an analytical framework integrating Transition Studies, Strategic Niche Management, and learning theories to systematically analyse barriers, enablers, and meta-factors influencing LL outcomes. The framework spans structural (actors, institutions, technologies), processual (context, inputs, governance, outputs, impacts), and learning dimensions. A mixed-methods approach combines a systematic literature review (159 articles) with practitioner workshops to validate findings. Interim results reveal a bias toward institutional and governance factors, with gaps in learning processes and long-term impacts. The study aims to translate insights into a practical management tool for LL design and scaling, bridging academic and practitioner needs. By synthesizing dispersed knowledge, this work advances understanding of LLs' transformative potential and offers actionable guidance for real-world implementation. Future steps include finalizing the framework and refining the tool through co-creation with stakeholders.

Key words

Living Lab, Transition, Barriers, Enablers, Meta-Factors, Learning

Introduction

With increasing popularity and utilisation of Living Labs (LL) both as methods and research settings, knowledge on factors influencing their development, directionality and outputs has become highly relevant. Multiple studies review factors influencing LL (Berberi et al., 2023; Valkokari et al., 2024), however, many focus on specific contexts, actor constellations, or thematic domains, making it difficult to draw generalizable insights. Moreover, the enabling and constraining factors identified in these studies are often embedded within broader narratives or described implicitly, rather than systematically extracted and compared. As a result, the wealth of empirical knowledge on LL remains fragmented, limiting its utility for practitioners seeking guidance on how to design, implement, or adapt in complex environments.

To address this gap, there is a need to systematically distil learnings across multiple LL case studies—especially those that touch on barriers and enablers of transformative outcomes, even if only indirectly. Grounding this synthesis in transition theory (TT) provides a robust conceptual lens for understanding how LL interact with wider socio-technical systems, how they navigate multi-level dynamics, and under what conditions they can contribute to systemic change. However, there are few attempts to review factors influencing LL from the perspective of transition studies (van Waes et al., 2021) despite increasing interest in LL as innovation and experimentation settings in the transition studies community (Puerari et al., 2018; Bulkeley et al., 2019; McCrory et al., 2020).

This paper presents a novel analytical framework designed to bridge this gap. Drawing on living lab, real world lab and transition studies literature, we propose a framework that allows a systematic synthesis of factors influencing LL, and a methodology to validate this framework both with existing literature and LL practitioners. We aim to create a methodologically sound and replicable process that helps identify, cluster, and interpret key factors that influence LL success in transition contexts. Through drawing on multiple fields of research, such an approach can help recognise research gaps and synthesise dispersed knowledge, advancing understanding of the transition potential of LL and providing practice-oriented guidance.

Literature review and development of analytical framework

In transition studies, living labs are conceptualised as sustainability labs (McCrory et al., 2022), respectively sustainability experiments (Sengers et al., 2019), implemented

primarily in urban environments (Bulkeley et al., 2019, von Wirth et al., 2019). Studies exploring living labs in transition contexts (van Waes et al., 2021) have utilised the Strategic Niche Management (SNM) framework, focusing on the creation and management of protected spaces, “niches”, at the micro-level of socio-technical transitions (Smith and Raven, 2012; Turnheim and Geels, 2019), to describe and categorise empirical observations on dynamics of and relationships within Living Labs described as challenges and dilemmas (van Waes et al., 2021).

This paper further explores the use of transition studies frameworks to analyse LL by extending the focus to the structure of the living labs, conceptualising the macro- and meso level of living labs (Schuurman, 2015) as small scale socio-technical (ST) systems consisting of actors, technologies and institutions (Kanger and Schot, 2019) with configurations differing from incumbent ST systems. Therefore, a structural analysis of LL through a transition framework lens (Köhler et al., 2019) is made possible. A further expansion of the analytical framework is done by adding learning theories to the learning functions observed by (van Waes et al., 2021). Learning (and knowledge) diffusion from LL into the wider society is indeed understudied but a vital part of understanding the role of LL in transitions (Bhatta et al., 2025).

Thus, by developing an analytical framework combining SNM, a ST system perspective and learning theories framework, this study explores transitions perspectives on LL, as well as human, institutional and technological factors (Knieling et al., 2021) influencing LL within broader transition processes. This expands the work done by previous studies (van Waes et al., 2021; Berberi et al., 2023), hence responding to a recognised need for theoretical work in the LL community (Della Santa et al., 2024) and providing a starting point for future exploration of the role of LL in socio-technical transitions (Schäpke et al., 2024).

The proposed framework consists of three dimensions: two main dimensions relating to the structure and processes of a LL, and a third – transversal – dimension focusing on learning. The first dimension of the framework consists of the main elements of a ST system: actors/networks, institutions and technologies/infrastructures (Kanger and Schot, 2019).

To capture the key components of the LL process, we identified and compared various LL frameworks proposed and applied in scholarly and practitioner-oriented publications¹

¹ For this, we conducted a focused mini-literature review across Web of Science, Scopus, and ENOLL Conference Proceedings (2021–2024) to identify key components of LL frameworks.

(See Annex 1 for an overview of the frameworks identified). From this analysis, we extracted and synthesized the seven most referenced elements of LL processes – context, inputs, governance, processes, outputs, outcomes, impact—, which now serve as the core categories of our second dimension. These represent a balanced and representative abstraction of how LL activities are conceptualized across different domains and contexts, containing the context in whom the living lab is situated, inputs into the lab, governance and processes, as well as the change enacted by the lab in terms of direct outputs, outcomes and impacts (Belcher and Claus, 2020).

The diagram (Figure 1) below shows the relationship of the two main dimensions, with the definitions for the individual concepts provided in Table 1. Figure 1 also shows some examples of how factors influencing LL activities could be classified using the analytical framework.

Figure 1. Conceptualisation of the main dimensions of the analytical framework

Table 1. Definitions of concepts used in initial version of the framework.

Concept	Working definition
Socio-technical system	Configuration of actors, technologies and institutions for fulfilling a certain societal function; manifestations (phenotype) of regimes (Kanger and Schot, 2019)
Actors/networks	<i>Actors</i> may be firms, e.g. users, suppliers or venture capitalists, or other organisations. <i>Networks</i> are an intermediate form of organization between hierarchies (internal organization within entities such as firms) and markets. (Jacobsson and Bergek, 2004)
Institutions	Institutions are the normative structures which promote stable patterns of social interactions/transactions necessary for the performance of vital societal functions (Jacobsson and Bergek, 2004)
Technology/infrastructure	A basic technology is a technological paradigm or core technology. At higher levels of complexity, the core may be a cluster of technologies, each of which follows a particular trajectory (Carlsson and Stankiewicz, 1991)
<i>Contextual and process levels</i>	
Context	Living labs mainly take place in real-life environments, respectively real-life settings (Schuurman et al., 2025)
Inputs	Inputs are contributions to and investments in the sustainability transition experiment (Forrest and Wiek, 2014)
Governance	The governance perspective deals with the organisation of the Living Lab as a whole and the interaction between its members (Vervoort et al., 2022)
Processes	Processes are a sequence of actions conducted in sustainability transition experiments. The particular actions and their sequence are critical for creating desired outputs (Forrest and Wiek, 2014)
Outputs	Outputs are direct results of LL experiments, or activities (Luederitz et al., 2017)
Outcomes	Outcomes refer to sustainability-related accomplishments of the experiment (Forrest and Wiek, 2014, Luederitz et al., 2017)
Impacts	Impacts encompass both physical change through innovations in technologies and infrastructures, and social changes (Bernert et al., 2024, Schöpke et al., 2024)

With the analytical framework barriers and enablers of LL can be categorized across components of the two above-described dimensions. Factors can be connected to one or multiple system components, shown on the vertical axis on the left-hand side of the diagram, and allocated to one or more processual elements, shown on the horizontal axis. The framework also distinguishes between internal and external factors, with internal factors referring to factors entirely under the control of the LL, respectively its actors and without influence from the external context, while external factors are defined as being outside of the control of the LL and influenced entirely by the external context.

In the examples highlighted in Figure 1, we can see how the same factor can play a different role at different stages of the LL process, requiring different action from the LL managers and participants, depending on the stage of the process. For instance, on the actor/network dimension, when planning and setting-up a LL actor mapping should be completed and political buy-in is identified in a local authority. The ideal way to leverage political buy-in (which is often classified as a key enabler of LLs) is to incorporate the local authority with an active, maybe even a leadership role, in several of the LL activities.

However, if such buy-in is not identified, the LL activities can be organized targeting increased political buy-in from the local authority as an outcome/impact of the interventions, turning a barrier into an enabler for future LL activities. Similarly, knowing that user-friendly technologies for data collection are an enabler of LL activities, LL managers could pre-test different technology alternatives to choose the most applicable and user-friendly one, or if resources are constrained focus on low-budget activities in the early stages of the LL implementation, conducting training and technology capacity building activities with LL users.

As illustrated in the examples above, the enabling factors can present an evolution during the LL process. This evolution often occurs thanks to learning processes due to LL interventions and the LL context. To reflect this, in a second step, learning will be added as a third framework dimension, focusing on capturing learning processes in the form of individual, organisational and societal learning (Pettersen et al., 2018; Bhatta et al., 2025) A potential visualization of the expanded framework as well as the conceptual definitions are provided below (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Extended framework including learning

Table 2. Definitions of learning concepts

Learning	Working definition
Individual learning	Learning of competencies learning (Pettersen et al., 2018; Bhatta et al., 2025)
Organisational learning	Learning within entities (i.e. teams/organisations) learning (Pettersen et al., 2018; Bhatta et al., 2025)
Societal learning	Learning across different stakeholders learning (Pettersen et al., 2018; Bhatta et al., 2025)

Methodology

To validate the applicability of the framework, we propose two-step approach, combining a systematic literature review of LL research, with a validation from practitioners, based on co-creative workshops with living lab practitioners.

For the first validation step, we utilize the above-described analytical framework as the base coding system to be implemented for the synthesis of the findings from the systematic LL literature review. This coding system (Annex 2). For the systematic literature review, a keyword search was conducted in Web of Science and Scopus using a predefined keyword string, initially yielding 252 results. After initial abstract and title screening using exclusion criteria, removing duplicates, and adding several articles using a snowballing method, 186 articles were retained for the coding stage². The retained articles are currently being coded utilizing the theoretical framework, with 68 papers having been reviewed at the time of writing of this research-in progress paper. After the finalization of the coding process, the authors of this paper, will conduct a synthesis and validation analysis of the categories proposed in the framework, identifying if some categories should be merged, expanded (i.e. divided into subcategories), or if new categories are needed to provide a systemic and comprehensive understanding of the enablers and barriers of LL.

For the second validation step, the proposed framework, as well as the coded categories will be presented to LL practitioners in one or two co-creative workshops. The final list of participants is yet to be decided but it includes LL managers from six active Swiss LLs and potentially additional living lab practitioners. The validation of the coded secondary data and addition of primary data inputs will add valuable insights from practitioners, as well as allow the research team to implement a needs-based development of a practice-oriented management tool for LL managers, which summarizes barriers and enablers and how they can be dealt with in the different stages of the LL implementation. The methodology is summarized in Figure 3 below:

² The exclusion criteria focused on a) date of publication, where a cutoff date of 2014 or more recent was set, with exceptions made for seminal publications, b) the publication source, focusing on scientific journals and the proceedings of the annual Open Living Lab Days conferences and c) a focus on environmental sustainability and/or well-being.

Figure 3. Overview of the methodology

Interim Results

Initial coding results (Table 3) indicate a potential imbalance of identified factors, with most factors assigned to the system elements “institution”, and “actor/network”, reflected in large number of codes for “process” and “governance”. On the other hand, learning factors were only addressed in small number of reviewed articles so far. However, these appear more balanced this far. One reason for this imbalance is the strong focus of many studies on institutional elements of LL processes, with less attention on material elements, external contexts, outputs, outcomes and impacts of the lab, the latter being a recognized shortcoming of the LL research field (Paskaleva and Cooper, 2021).

Codesystem	Impact	Outcomes	Outputs	Processes	Governance	Inputs	Context	
Learning								
Organizational	5	11	2	11	5	2		
Societal	9	9	5	8	4		2	
Individual	2	8	4	13	6	3	1	
Structure (1st dimension)								
Unclear	1	4	1	5	3	1	5	
Institution	10	38	13	127	167	35	58	
Technology/Infrastructure	5	12	10	24	10	22	9	
Actor/Network	9	26	14	94	102	62	37	
Influence								
Unclear				3	13	3	5	
Both	1	2	1	15	15	5	4	
Barrier	3	9	3	33	40	21	44	
Enabler	21	61	29	170	183	83	47	
SUMME	0	66	180	82	503	548	237	212

Table 3: Overview of interim results (n coded = 77 out of 159)

Note: Crosstabulation interim coding results, showing cross-relations between categories of the structural (1) and process dimensions (2) as well as the learning and enabler/barrier categories.

In the next step, the research team will complete the coding of the entire dataset and then create an initial set of factor categories, with each category being representative of a meta-factor. This initial meta-factor typology will subsequently undergo a first round of validation, followed by an adaptation based on the inputs from the validation co-creation workshop. In parallel with this adaptation, a first draft of the management tool will be created based on the practitioner’s input, with both the tool and the final typology re-validated in the second co-creation workshop.

Discussion & conclusion

In this paper, we have developed an analytical framework based on transition, LL and learning theories to systematically analyse factors influencing LL across the largely practice-oriented body of LL literature. Our aim was to expand on existing work by developing a multidimensional framework able to explore individual cases from several perspectives, allowing a deeper understanding of enablers and barriers affecting both LL processes and structures.

The preliminary results indicate that the framework is comprehensive and able to classify barriers and enablers identified in a systematic review of LL literature. While there is a high degree of heterogeneity in terms of factor definitions and understanding (e.g. co-creation, engagement or even the exact definition of a LL), this is not a shortcoming of the framework itself, but rather an issue that should be addressed by the field and considered in future work.

The literature sources reviewed so far allow us to identify biases in the LL literature in the structural dimension towards actors and institutional factors, and in the process dimension towards LL governance and processes. While this is unsurprising, it also highlights research gaps regarding the role of technologies respectively inputs and outputs, outcomes and impacts for successful implementation of LLs. Finally, the third selected dimension, learning, is underrepresented across the reviewed body of literature despite being highly relevant for experimentation and scaling up of innovations with high transition potential.

Our work will continue through coding of the remaining literature, upon completion of which a co-creation process with LL practitioners will be started with the aim of developing a final version of the framework and based on it, a typology of barriers and enablers for LLs. This addition to research will be accompanied by the co-development of a management tool for LL managers, supporting practical implementation of LL structures and processes.

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3. Bernert, P., Weiser, A., Kampfmann, T., Lang, D.J., 2024. Impacts beyond experimentation - Conceptualising emergent impacts from long-term real-world laboratory processes. *GAIA - Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society* 33, 18–25.
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Annex 1 – Overview of the frameworks found in the literature review and used to build the second-dimension categories

The overview below shows the frameworks identified in the literature review, the categories included in each of the frameworks, and **highlights** the categories that were selected for the analytical framework used in this article.

Scopus and Web of science search "Living Labs" frameworks

Bouwma, I; Wigboldus, S; Potters, J; Selnes, T; van Rooij, S; Westerink, J (2022). *Sustainability Transitions and the Contribution of Living Labs: A Framework to Assess Collective Capabilities and Contextual Performance*. DOI: 10.3390/su142315628

- Design and set up of the LL
- LL interactions
- Positioning and reputation of the LL – **proxy: context**
- LL actions – **proxy: process**
- LL products and services – **proxy: outputs**
- **Outcomes and impact of LL**

Mbatha, S.P.; Musango, J.K. (2022). *A Systematic Review on the Application of the Living Lab Concept and Role of Stakeholders in the Energy Sector*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114009>

- Problem or challenge addressed
- **Application context**
- Category of the LL
- Field of application of LL
- Stakeholders involved and their role – **proxy: governance**
- Monitoring and evaluation – **proxy: outcomes and impact**

Conference proceedings search

Vervoort, K., Konstantinidis, E., Santonen, T., Petsani, D., Servais, D., 2022. *Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardised evaluation framework*. Presented at the XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference "Innovating in a Digital World," Copenhagen, Denmark. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371315414_Harmonizing_the_evaluation_of_living_labs_a_standardized_evaluation_framework

- Strategy of the LL
- Operations in the LL – proxy: process
- Openness of the LL
- Users and reality
- Impact and value creation
- Stability and harmonisation

Maria Kiseleva (2021). *Agroecology living labs: defining characteristics and key components of their successful orchestration*. 2021 ENOLL Conference Proceedings: <https://enoll.org/publications/>

- Topic
- Aims and goals
- Activities, approaches and methods – proxy: process
- Context
- Structure – proxy: governance
- Infrastructure – proxy: inputs
- Long term vision
- Shareholders

Habibipour, A., Lindberg, J., Runardotter, M., Elmistikawy, Y., Ståhlbröst, A., Chronéer, D. (2021). *Rural Living Lab: What is that and how is it shaped?* 2021 ENOLL Conference Proceedings: <https://enoll.org/publications/>

- Nature and Philosophy
- Scope of the LL (timewise)
- Innovation development phases
- ICT and digital innovation (maturity levels) – proxy: inputs
- Governance level
- Actors
- Vision

Scopus and Web of Science search "Real-world Labs" (Reallabore) frameworks

Luederitz, C., Schöpke, N., Wiek, A., Lang, D.J., Bergmann, M., Bos, J.J., Burch, S., Davies, A., Evans, J., König, A., Farrelly, M.A., Forrest, N., Frantzeskaki, N., Gibson, R.B., Kay, B., Loorbach, D., McCormick, K., Parodi, O., Rauschmayer, F., Schneidewind, U., Stauffacher, M., Stelzer, F., Trencher, G., Venjakob, J., Vergragt, P.J., von Wehrden, H., Westley, F.R., (2017). *Learning through evaluation – A tentative evaluative scheme for sustainability transition experiments*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.09.005>

- Inputs

- Processes
- Outcomes
- Outputs

Learning frameworks

Pettersson, F., Westerdahl, S., & Hansson, J., 2018. Learning through collaboration in the Swedish public transport sector? Co-production through guidelines and living labs. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 69, 394-401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2018.07.010>

- Individual learning
- Team learning
- Organisational learning

Bhatta, A., Vreugdenhil, H., & Slinger, J., 2025. Harvesting living labs outcomes through learning pathways. *Current Research in Environmental Sustainability*, 9, 100277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crsust.2024.100277>

- Individual (learning) level
- Team (learning) level
- Intra, organisational, systemic (learning) level- proxy societal learning

The table below shows the categories identified in other papers in the literature review, which were discarded due to the lack of inclusion of a comprehensive analytical or theoretical framework that brings together the different categories. We include this overview here since those discarded papers were still useful to inform the naming of the categories selected for the analytical framework used, which are also highlighted.

Paper/article	Categories included
van Waes, A., Nikolaeva, A., Raven, R., (2021). <i>Challenges and dilemmas in strategic urban experimentation An analysis of four cycling innovation living labs</i> . <i>Technological Forecasting and Social Change</i> 172, 121004. van Waes et al., 2021	Visions and Expectations Network, Actors and Resources Learning
Berberi, A., Beaudoin, C., McPhee, C., Guay, J., Bronson, K., Nguyen, V.M. (2023). <i>Enablers, barriers, and future considerations for living lab effectiveness in environmental and agricultural sustainability transitions: a review of studies evaluating living labs</i> . <i>Local Environment</i> 1-19. https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2023.2238750	Governance Process Features of the LL Characteristics of the participants Social dimensions Training and research Technology Beyond the LL
Galway, L.P.; Levkoe, C.Z.; Portinga, R.L.W.; Milun, K. A (2022) <i>Scoping Review Examining Governance, Co-Creation, and Social and Ecological Justice in Living Labs Literature</i> . DOI: https://doi.org/10.3390/challe13010001	Governance Participants Key processes used Intended outcomes General descriptor term

<p>McCrorry, G., Schöpke, N., Holmén, J. et al (2020). <i>Sustainability-oriented labs in real-world contexts: An exploratory review.</i> DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123202</p>	<p>Space Process Organization – proxy: governance Interrelations amongst characteristics Sustainability</p>
<p>Hossain, M., Leminen, S., Westerlund, M., (2019). <i>A systematic review of living lab literature.</i> DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.257</p>	<p>Temporality Governance Unforeseen outcomes Efficiency Recruitment of user groups Sustainability and scalability of innovation activities</p>
<p>Santonen, T., Petronikolou, S., Petsani, D., Dimitriadis, S., Bamidis, P., Konstantinidis, E. (2023) <i>Towards living lab value proposition: Living lab experts' perceptions on living lab</i> OLLD conference proceedings 2023: https://enoll.org/publications/</p>	<p>Economic benefits Improved Innovation Validity and Reliability Benefits for the users and society – proxy: impact Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities Safe environment for RDI Increased skills and capabilities – proxy: impact</p>
<p>Enseñado, E.M.; Kammerer, L.; Den Dekker, J.; Liongo, I.; Aamot, T.I.; Quadros A.; Vanelli, F.; Makousiari, E.; Nercua W.; Caruso, R.; Vervoort, K.; de los Rios White, M.; Asier Undabeitia P., Tiwari, A. Iulia A., Gharbia, S. (2023) <i>Towards a methodology for monitoring and evaluating living labs: Insights from the early stages within the SCORE Project.</i> OLLD conference proceedings 2023: https://enoll.org/publications/</p>	<p>Objectives Resources – proxy: inputs Organization – proxy: governance Process Activities Participants Solutions – proxy: outputs and outcomes Tools Communication Knowledge sharing</p>
<p>Peyvand Forouzandeh (2021). <i>Investigating the emerging landscape and key enabling factors in creating the diversity of urban collaborative experimentations in Canada to accelerate sustainability transition; qualitative case studies from four major Canadian cities.</i> 2021 ENOLL Conference Proceedings https://enoll.org/publications/</p>	<p>Relational, political, institutional factors – proxy: context Structural and local factors Performance and financial sustainability factors Interpersonal, ideological, and individual factors</p>
<p>Bergmann, M., Schöpke, N., Marg, O., Stelzer, F., Lang, D.J., Bossert, M., Gantert, M., Häußler, E., Marquardt, E., Piontek, F.M., Potthast, T., Rhodius, R., Rudolph, M., Ruddat, M., Seebacher, A., Sußmann, N., (2021). <i>Transdisciplinary sustainability research in real-world labs: success factors and methods for change.</i> https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00886-8</p>	<p>Contribute to transformation – proxy: impact Experimentation method Transdisciplinary research mode Long-term orientation, scalability and transferability Learning and reflexivity Diverse (related to transformation experimentation etc.)</p>

Annex 2 – Coding system used for systematic literature review

The table below shows full coding system used in our literature review, and the number of codes that have been assigned under each category currently.